

MICROSTRUCTURE AND PROPERTIES OF IN-SITU TiB₂ PARTICLE REINFORCED AL-4.5Cu COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In-situ TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu aluminum-matrix composites were prepared by the salt-metal reactions using two salts of K₂TiF₆ and KBF₄. More refined in-situ TiB₂ reinforcement particles were produced with addition of specific flux in the reaction salts, control of processing temperature and mechanical stirring. X-ray diffraction was introduced to confirm the formation of TiB₂ phase, and no other intermediate phases like Al₃Ti were found in the composites. The scanning electron microscopy analysis was introduced to analyze the distribution and size of TiB₂ particles. The results also show that TiB₂ particles are uniformly distributed in the matrix without large agglomerations. The size of TiB₂ particles is measured to be under 0.4µm in diameter. Some TiB₂ particles are gathering along the grain boundary regions. The grains are effectively refined, and extremely refined equiaxial grains are formed after stirring at 360rpm speed. The ultimate tensile strength and yield stress of the in-situ TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu matrix composite are respectively improved by 51% and 75% in comparison with the matrix alloy. According to Orowan strengthening and fine-grain strengthening theories, the uniformly distributed fine TiB₂ reinforcement particles and the effectively refined grain size contribute to the improvement of mechanical properties.

1. INTRODUCTION

The introduction of secondary phases like ceramic particle reinforcement can strengthen the matrix materials according to the Orowan strengthening mechanism [1]. Thus the particulates reinforced aluminum matrix composites (PRAMCs) are promising materials for the application in structure, transportation, aerospace and the military applications. A number of studies focus on PRAMCs because of their outstanding combination of mechanical properties, such as high specific strength, modulus, hardness and low thermal expansion coefficient [2, 3]. Among various potential particulate reinforcements such as: B₄C, SiC, Si₃N₄, TiC, TiB₂, Al₂O₃ [4-9], TiB₂ particle is portrayed to be an outstanding reinforcement in aluminum because of its good thermodynamic stability, high hardness, high melting point, high modulus, high corrosion resistance and low density [10-12]. Among various aluminum alloys, Al-Cu alloys have high strength, high hardness and high heat resistance, but low in

corrosion resistance. Therefore the introduction of high hardness TiB₂ particles into Al-Cu alloy has been studied for better mechanical properties and corrosion resistance of Al-Cu alloys [13-15].

During the preparations for PRAMCs, the composites synthesized by in-situ processes have a clearer interface between matrix and reinforcement, and a better matrix–reinforcement interfacial thermodynamic stability compared with exogenously-formed processes. Compare with other in-situ processes, the salt–metal reaction route is widely used to synthesis the in-situ TiB₂ particles for its advantages, namely: (a) The TiB₂ particles are formed by reactions in the melt and without wet problem; (b) the reaction temperature is lower than that in other reaction systems, and the size of the TiB₂ particles can be submicron; (c) the matrix–reinforcement interface is clean and stable; (d) bulk and continuous casting of composites are possible [15,16]. The following sequence is the exothermic process to form the TiB₂ particles [15]:

And the TiB₂ particles can also formed by a direct reaction [17]:

Researches have been done to study the in-situ process for the fabrication of TiB₂-containing metal matrix composites and the mechanism of TiB₂ formation during the process [16]. The distribution of the TiB₂ particles in the pure Al matrix have also been studied [18]. However, little study focuses on the TiB₂ particles reinforcement Al-Cu alloy composites, and the study of the TiB₂ particles reinforcement Al-Cu alloy composites with a big particle volume percentage is still scarcer so far.

In the present work, the in-situ 5vol% TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites are successful synthesized through the salt–metal reaction route with mechanical stirring at the reaction holding. The research is processed to study the distribution of the TiB₂ particles in the Al-Cu matrix and the mechanical properties of the in-situ 5vol% TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites. The factors affecting the distribution of the TiB₂ particles in the Al-Cu matrix and the effect of mechanical stirring on distribution of particles and grain refinement is discussed.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

In the present investigation, commercial pure Al (99.8%, wt%, the same below), pure Cu (99.9%) were used to prepare the Al-4.5Cu base metal. Two kind of chemically pure salts, potassium fluotitanate (K₂TiF₆) and potassium fluoborate (KBF₄) were used to synthesize the TiB₂ particle reinforcement. Specific flux was also used to help the reactions.

2.2 Processing

Aluminum ingot was first melted in a graphite crucible using a resistance furnace and the Cu for preparation of the base metal was added into the melt at 700°C, then the melt was heated up to 830°C. The K₂TiF₆ and KBF₄ salts, thoroughly mixed with specific flux, were added into the melt after 2h preheating at 300°C. When the salts are being added, the temperature of the melt was controlled below 830°C without any big ups and downs. The reaction holding time was set at 40min with mechanical stirring which was introduced by a graphite stirring bar, the stirring bar was set below the interface of

the melt and salts as shown in Fig.1, the stirring speed was set at 0, 180 and 360rpm respectively. After the reaction holding, the slag was removed and the melt was cooled down to 720 °C, and casted into a permanent mould preheated at 200 °C.

Fig.1 Sketch of mechanical stirring.

2.3 Characterization

Specimens of the composites for metallographic examination were cut from the ends of tensile test samples, then grinded, polished and etched by solution with 0.5% HF slightly and deeply respectively. An Axiovert 200MAT optical microscopes and a JSM-7600F scanning electron microscope with an IncaX-Max 50 energy dispersive X-ray analysis was employed to examine the microstructures of the composites. A XRD-7000S X-ray diffractometer with Cu K α radiation operated at 40 kV and 40 mA was used to identify the phases in the composites. The room temperature (25 °C) tensile tests was conducted on a SHIMADZU AG-100KN tester with a 2mm/min crosshead speed. The average ultimate tensile strength (UTS) value was obtained from four samples for each specific condition. The average Rockwell hardness of three points on the sample surface was tested by 600MRD Rockwell hardness tester.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 In-situ formation of TiB₂ ceramic particles

The in-situ TiB₂ ceramic phase is successfully formed through the aluminothermic reaction of a complex potassium fluoride molten salt mixture. Figure 2 shows the X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns of the in-situ AMCs (Aluminum Matrix Composites) formed in present work at different conditions. The TiB₂ peaks can be found in all results, no any other peaks such as Al₃Ti or AlB₂ peaks can be found. It confirms the formation of TiB₂ ceramic phase and no any other intermediate phases is formed. The intensity of TiB₂ peaks in the no flux condition is weak compared with others due to the loss of elements caused by the gasification of salts. It is worth to note that the intensity of TiB₂ peaks with different stirring speed during the holding are almost the same, and no any other peaks of by-products like Al₂O₃ or K₃AlF₆ could be found. This confirms that stirring during holding does not have much influence on the yield of TiB₂ particles or lead to form intermediate phase, and high speed stirring

below the interface of melt and salts would not introduce any by-products into the composite. The Al_2Cu peaks have also been found.

Fig. 2. XRD diffraction patterns of the in-situ AMCs in different conditions: (a). no flux adding, (b). adding flux without stirring, (c). adding flux with 180rpm stirring, (d). adding flux with 360rpm stirring.

3.2 Microstructures

3.2.1 Effect of the specific flux on controlling agglomerations

Two kinds of salt powders are mixed with a molar ratio of $\text{Ti/B} = 1/2$, and the total mass of salts is set to synthesize 5vol% TiB_2 particles. The molten salts are form a very thick fluid layer, since the mass of salts is more than half the mass of the master metal and the molten salts are all floating on top of the melt, signs in Fig. 3a. The thick layer of molten melt not only inhibit the reaction but also make some salts get heated before fully contacting with the melt, which may lead to severe gasification and decomposition of the salts and high temperature in local melt. The local high temperature will accelerate the precipitation of intermediate phases at the place where the concentration of Ti or B is higher than the other [19] and further become the agglomerations with different morphologies and not easy to eliminate by the reaction holding (agglomerations are clusters when Ti is exceeded as shown in Fig 4a, and agglomerations are chain-like when B exceeded is shown in Fig 4b [20-22]).

Fig. 3 Sketch of effect of adding specific flux: (a). without adding flux, (b). with adding flux.

After adding specific flux, element Mg, contained in the flux, reacts with O₂ and form the MgO, The MgO which further reacts with the other part of the flux and form some compounds with high melting point which increases the viscosity of molten salt. With this change the molten salts become wrapping around the melt instead of floating on top, as shown in Fig. 3b. Thus the reaction area is expanded and the salts become easier to fully contact with the melt. The agglomerations caused by local high temperature and element concentration are reduced after adding the flux, as shown in Fig. 4c.

Fig 4 Influence of adding flux on reducing agglomerations:

- (a). clusters of TiB₂ when no flux adding, (b). chain-like agglomerations when no flux adding, (c). reduced agglomerations with adding of flux.

3.2.2 Particle distribution

Fig.5 Metallographic microstructures of the in-situ AMCs formed in different conditions:

- (a, b). without stirring, (c, d). with stirring at 180rpm (e, f) with stirring at 360rpm

Fig. 5 shows the metallographic microstructures of the in-situ AMCs formed in present work at different conditions. It is clearly found that the TiB₂ particles are uniformly distributed in the matrix

without large agglomeration in every situation. Most of TiB_2 particles are distributed along the grain boundary regions with some small agglomeration. With the introducing of mechanical stirring, the distribution of particles get more uniform and the grains become more refined. But mechanical stirring has no influence on the grain boundary distribution of particles.

Fig.6 SEM micrographs of the in-situ AMCs formed in different conditions: (a). agglomerations along grain boundary when no stirring, (b). dispersed particles when no stirring, (c). agglomerations along grain boundary when stirring at 180rpm, (d). dispersed particles when stirring at 180rpm, (e). agglomerations along grain boundary when stirring at 360rpm, (f). dispersed particles when stirring at 360rpm.

Fig. 6 is the SEM micrographs of the in-situ AMCs formed in present work at different conditions. From Fig. 6a, c, f, the trend to distribute along the grain boundary has been further confirmed in each condition. With the increase of stirring speed, the width of grain boundary is reduced because of a more uniformly distribution of particles in the whole melt. Although most of the TiB₂ particles gather along the grain boundary regions, dispersed TiB₂ particles still could found next to the grain boundary, as shown in Fig. 6b, d, e. It is worth to note that the dispersed TiB₂ particles near the grain boundary are not typical hexagonal morphology and some of them have no clear sharp corners and straight edges. The particle size of most dispersed TiB₂ is measured to be under 0.4μm in diameter. And the particle size has no obvious change with the increase of the stirring speed.

Although most TiB₂ particles gather along the grain boundary regions since they have been rejected by the growing solid phase at the solid/liquid interface during solidification, it is hard to find clear distinct particles contours in the agglomerations along the grain boundary. EDX is introduced to examine the element composition of the agglomerations, and the result is shown in Figure 7. Result shows that both Ti and B elements exist in the agglomeration (The B element has the smallest atomic weight in the elements which can be examined by EDX, so the atomic percentage of B element is not accurate and the atomic percentage of Ti element is small), the content of Cu element found in the agglomerations is high and the atomic ratio of Al/Cu is approximate to 2/1. It indicates that the Al₂Cu phase may wraps up the TiB₂ particles since the Al₂Cu phase in the binary Al-Cu alloy has a strong tendency to wet the TiB₂ particles [15].

Element	Weight percentage	Atomic percentage
B K	36.88	66.69
O K	3.02	3.69
Al K	23.87	17.29
Ti K	11.74	4.79
Cu L	24.49	7
Total	100.00	

Fig.7 EDX result of the agglomerations along the grain boundary regions.

For a further studying the formation of agglomeration along the grain boundary, samples are examined by SEM with deep etching. Fig. 8 shows the result in different conditions. A kind of extremely tiny particles, with sizes of 50-100nm, is found in agglomerations at different conditions. These particles adhere to the big ones. They may formed by the residual Ti and B in the liquid phase which is consumed at the final stage of solidification or directly precipitate in those liquid phase. And it is worth to note that particle with a more like hexagonal morphology was observed in the agglomeration after deeply etched. So a layer of Al₂Cu phase wetting around the TiB₂ particles may be the reason of there not being a typical hexagonal morphology and no clear sharp corners and straight edges for some particles.

With the evidence above, we assumed a possible explanation for the formation of agglomerations along the grain boundary without clear particles contours. During the solidification, the liquid Al₂Cu

phase wets and wraps up the TiB₂ particles and most particles are rejected by the growing solid phase at the solid/liquid interface. Then the particles gather at the residual liquid phase which is the grain boundary after solidification. The extremely tiny particles formed from the liquid phase fills the gaps of big particles with the Al₂Cu phase. Subsequently, the agglomerations without clear particles contours form at the end.

Fig. 8 SEM micrographs of the in-situ AMCs formed at different conditions after deep etch: (a). without stirring, (b). with stirring at 180rpm (c) with stirring at 360rpm.

3.2.3 Grain refinement

Grain refinement is an important advantage of composite. The mechanism of grain refinement in composite is composed of two main parts: first, the particle reinforcement may act as the heterogeneous nuclei for the matrix; second, particles will gather at the solidification interface and hinder the growth of the grains. In the TiB₂ particle reinforcement composite, these two parts are all effective. Although the TiB₂ particles cannot act as heterogeneous nuclei directly^[15], the intermediate phases Al₃Ti can act as a great heterogeneous nucleation nuclei of α -Al and peritectic reaction:

could happen during the solidification. With the presence of element B, the critical Ti concentration of the peritectic reaction can be reduced from 0.15% to 0.01%. So due to the different reaction speed of reaction 1 and 2, and the solute segregation, very small amounts of Al₃Ti will present in the composite and promotes heterogeneous nucleation. During the solidification, it is hard for TiB₂ particles to be captured by the solidification interface since they cannot be wet. So the TiB₂ particles will gather at the solidification interface and hinder the growth of the grains.

Fig. 9 Metallography of grains of the in-situ AMCs formed at different conditions: (a). matrix alloy, (b). without stirring, (c). with stirring at 180rpm (d). with stirring at 360rpm.

Fig. 9 shows the metallography of grains of the in-situ AMCs formed in present work at different conditions. It is worth to note that the grain size of the composite is dramatically refined compared

with the matrix, and with the increase of the stirring speed the grain size gets more refined. Even become extremely refined equiaxial grain at the stirring speed of 360rpm. Since the mechanical stirring temperature is far above the liquidus, the promotion of the grain reinforcement is mainly caused by homogenizing the solute and particles. The mechanical stirring homogenize the distribution of Ti and B element, so it is hard to precipitate and growth to big intermediate phases then some remained Al_3Ti become tinier and more uniform which provides more heterogeneous nuclei during the solidification. With a more uniform distribution of element B, there is less B-poor area in the melt, so the peritectic reaction of Ti and Al is easier to happen throughout the bulk melt. Meanwhile the mechanical stirring also homogenizes the distribution of TiB_2 particles which reduces the formation of agglomerations and makes the gathering of TiB_2 particles at the solidification interface become more uniform. Stirring below the interface of the melt and the molten salts make sure there is no any other by-products introduced into the melt, so the speed of stirring can be as high as 360rpm and the extremely refined equiaxial grain formed.

3.3 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

3.3.1 Tensile properties

Table. 1 shows the results of as-cast mechanical properties of the in-situ AMCs in present work at different conditions. It is clearly shown that the yield stress has been improved by 26%, 46%, 75% with the reinforcement of the AMCs with stirring at 0, 180, 360rpm respectively. The improvement of UTS is 28%, 34%, 51% respectively. But the ductility of the composites is all reduced compared with the matrix, and the ductility has an increase with the raise of stirring speed. The changes of the tensile properties may mainly be caused by the introduction of the reinforcement particles since there is no heat treatment in present works.

Table. 1 As-cast mechanical properties of the in-situ AMCs formed at different conditions.

Specimens	Stirring speed (Rpm)	Yield stress (MPa)	UTS (MPa)	Ductility (%)	Hardness (HRA)
Matrix	0	65	166	12.50	19.0
AMC	0	82	212	5.65	26.1
AMC	180	95	223	6.25	32.7
AMC	360	114	251	7.05	35.1

There are two main parts of the reinforcement of tensile properties, the distribution of particles and the refinement of grains. For yield stress, the dispersed particles under $0.4\mu m$ can be a suitable reinforcement for the Orowan strengthening mechanism and in the dislocation glide during the loading the dislocation line is more likely to loop around the particles rather than cut through this particles for Orowan looping, the interaction of dislocation loops gives more resistance of dislocation movement then increases the yield stress of composites with a high volume percentage of particles. The particles distributed along the grain boundary can effectively hinder the dislocation slip, and with the extremely tiny particles filled in the gaps, the effect of acting as obstacles of dislocation slip gets stronger. For grain refinement, a refined grain can reduce the slip length and thus delaying the crack nucleation and

increasing the ductility. The Hall-Petch relationship shows the effect of grain size on the mechanical properties of composites and yield stress is increasing when grain size decrease.

With the introduction of mechanical stirring, the distribution of particles gets more uniform and the grain size gets more refined when the stirring speed is increased. So the yield stress and the UTS are all increased when at a higher stirring speed situation. The UTS of composite is not improved as effectively as the yield stress, which is mainly due to the cast defects and some small inclusions. It is worth to note that the reduction of ductility is the result of the inclusions or agglomeration and it is still increasing with the increasing of stirring speed.

With more uniformly distribution of particles and more refined grains, the hardness of composites also get an effective improvement by 37%, 72%, 85% which are higher than the matrix at 0, 180, 360rpm mechanical stirring, respectively.

3.3.2 Fractography

Fig. 10 shows the fractography of the in-situ AMCs formed in present work at different conditions. When there is no mechanical stirring during reaction holding, some agglomerations cut the matrix and it is hard to find small dimples. With the mechanical stirring during reaction holding, the cutting of agglomeration gets less at 180rpm stirring speed but some area still can found a lot particles gather at the bottom of small dimples. When stirring speed raised to 360rpm, it is hard to find agglomerations cutting the matrix and particles which are distributing at the bottom of small dimples uniformly shows a good bonding with the matrix.

Fig. 10 Fractography of the in-situ AMCs formed at different conditions: (a). without stirring, (b). with stirring at 180rpm (c). with stirring at 360rpm.

4. CONCLUSIONS

1. The 5vol% TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites are successfully prepared with a better processing. TiB₂ particles are uniformly distributed without intermediate phases like Al₃Ti or AlB₂. The size of TiB₂ particles is under 0.4µm in diameter. The grains of the matrix are effectively refined.

2. With the mechanical stirring during the reaction holding, the distribution of particles is much uniform and more effective with the increasing of stirring speed. The grain size also gets more refined with the increase of the stirring speed and extremely refined equiaxial grains are formed at the 360rpm stirring speed.

3. The formation of agglomerations along the grain boundary without clear particles contours is explained. The extremely tiny particles fill the gaps of bigger particles with the Al₂Cu phase which wet the TiB₂ particles.

4. The mechanical properties of TiB₂/Al-4.5Cu composites have a great improvement compared with the matrix alloy with the decrease of ductility. The yield stress has been improved by 26%, 46%, 75% with the reinforcement of the AMCs with stirring at 0, 180, 360rpm respectively and the improvement of UTS is 28%, 34%, 51% respectively.

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